

A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY ON THE MULTI-SOLVENT PROFILING AND BIOACTIVITY STUDY OF ANTI-DIABETIC AND CYTOTOXIC ACTION OF POMEGRANATE LEAF EXTRACTS

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Abstract

Nature has always been a promising source of therapeutic substances. Use of herbal products is increasing day by day due to their high acceptability, low-cost and lesser side-effects. Cancer and Diabetes mellitus (DM) are among the leading causes of death now a day. Both of these problems have been positively experimented using the extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*. The plant of interest in present study is *Punica granatum*, which belongs to family Lythraceae (Punicaceae) and part used is the leaves. The plant has been reported to have various pharmacological effects like anti-oxidant, anti-cancer, anti-diabetic, anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, anti-arthritis, anti-glycation, anti-atherosclerotic, hypolipidemic, anti-hypertensive, hepato-protective, nephro-protective etc. The objective of present study is to evaluate anti-diabetic as well as anti-cancer potential of leaves of *Punica granatum*. Extracts in various solvents (n-hexane, chloroform, methanol, ethanol and distilled water) were prepared from powdered leaves of *Punica granatum* by applying hot and cold extraction methods. Proximate analysis, fourier transform infra-red (FTIR) spectral comparison, mineral estimation (using atomic absorption spectroscopy) and UV-visible scan was performed on powder and extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*. Anti-cancer potential was evaluated by performing methyl-thiazolyl-tetrazolium (MTT) assay on HepG2 cell line using 50µl, 100µl concentrations of n-hexane, chloroform and ethanol extracts. Anti-diabetic activity was investigated by performing in vitro

*α -amylase inhibition assay and glucose uptake by yeast cell assay using five (n-hexane, chloroform, methanol, distilled water, ethanol) extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*. Acarbose was used as standard for α -amylase inhibition assay and metronidazole was the standard drug in glucose uptake by yeast cells assay. Results of anti-cancer activity showed no significant inhibitory effect that might be due to short interval of time provided in MTT assay. All extracts showed significant increase in glucose uptake by yeast cells with the highest effect shown by n-hexane extract while all other tested extracts also significantly increased the glucose uptake by yeast cells relative to standard (metronidazole). While, only n-Hexane extract showed significant alpha-amylase inhibition compared to standard (acarbose).*

1.1 INTRODUCTION

1.1.1 Therapeutic Importance of Plants

Man has always been seeking for medicines since ancient times. Fifty % of modern drugs are estimated to be originated from plants in one or another way (Sharma et al., 2021). Use of herbal products for healing purpose is as old as the history of mankind. Herbal products are being used for treatment of diverse medical conditions since thousands of years (Van Arsdall, 2023). Sixty % of modern anti-neoplastic remedies and 75% anti-infective drugs are of natural origin (Yeh, 2022). Recent research suggests that herbs are useful in numerous pathological states including hypertension, depression, diabetes, pain and migraine. Herbals have the ability to have protective action against the toxic effects of heavy metals and drug-induced adverse effects (Bavarsad et al., 2023). In the beginning, herbal products were used as teas, poultices, tinctures, powders and other preparations (Izah et al., 2024). The isolation of morphine from poppy plant served as a breakthrough and consequential separation of therapeutically active moieties from plants led to the use of herbs as medication (Teuscher & Lindequist, 2023).

WHO reported in 2008 that about 80% people around the globe use traditional herbal remedies for major health issues because herbal drugs are cheaper, have longer shelf-life and lesser undesired effects (Tangkiatkumjai et al., 2020). Above 500 historic communities used approximately 800 herbal species for treating various ailments (Giannenas et al., 2020).

1.1.2 Cancer and anti-cancer potential of herbal drugs

Cancer is the uncontrolled proliferation of cells which can attack and destroy other healthy tissues and organs. The spreading of cancerous cells to other parts of body is termed as metastasis (Chandraprasad et al., 2022) (Kotamkar et al., 2021) Cancer is the leading cause of fatality in humans (Rumgay et al., 2022). Above 200 types of human cancer are known today in above 60 body organs (Bonsignore et al., 2021) with majority classified into 4 main stages; stage I, II, III, IV while some are said to be at zero (0) stage (Patil & Bellary, 2022). Various factors are considered to pose a risk for cancer such as alcohol-consumption, lack of physical activity, obesity, smoking, oxidative stress, prolonged exposure to sunshine, environmental pollutants and poor diet (Wadgaonkar, 2024)

Cancer treatment strategies include the use of radiations (radiotherapy), chemical substances (chemotherapy) and surgical approaches (Debela et al., 2021). Resistance to chemotherapeutic agents observed recently has led to the need for development and search for less noxious and more effective anti-cancer drugs (Rezayatmand et al., 2022).

Herbal drugs are very valuable for prevention and treatment of tumors. Natural anti-cancer drugs (like vinca alkaloids, etoposide, taxols) have lesser unwanted effects and better efficacy as compared to chemotherapeutic agents (steroidal analogues, alkylating agents, antibiotics). Herbal drugs show anti-cancer effect by various mechanisms like (1) inhibition of cancer-promoting enzymes, (2) up-regulation of protective enzymes, (3) enhancing

immune function and (4) induction of anti-oxidant action. Some natural drugs have preventive action by strengthening detoxification abilities of body while others inhibit growth of cancerous cells by regulating the action of certain enzymes and hormones. Some herbals decrease toxicity of chemotherapeutic agents and radiations (Obafemi & Besong, 2023). Various familiar chemotherapeutic agents like podophyllotoxin, camptothecin and paclitaxel are of herbal origin (Esmeeta et al., 2022).

Human cancerous cell lines are the cells derived from the culture of a particular body organ and show the same attributes of the chosen cell population usually classified as primary cell cultures (contains the cells obtained directly from a specific cell) and secondary cell cultures (contain the cells which are obtained as a result of sub-culturing of the primary cells) (Richter et al., 2021). An assortment of human cancerous cell lines includes HT29 (colon tumor cell line), AGS (gastric cancer cell line), MCF-7 (breast tumor cell line), Hep-G2 (hepatoma cell line) (Ramu & Ahmed, 2022).

1.1.3 Diabetes mellitus and anti-diabetic potential of herbals

Diabetes mellitus (DM), a group of metabolic disorders distinguished mainly by elevated serum glucose level (hyperglycemia) may result from defective insulin secretion, insulin action, or both (Dilworth et al., 2021). It results from metabolic disturbance and may be either type-I (inborn, insulin dependent) or type II (acquired, non-insulin dependent) caused by altered food metabolism which leads to hyperglycemia (Jiang et al., 2020). DM intensifies the incidence of atherosclerosis, lipoprotein metabolism abnormalities, cerebro-vascular problems, hypertension, cardiovascular and peripheral arterial diseases (Sajed, 2022). During the last

decade, DM has caused the likelihood of cardiovascular diseases to increase 2 to 5 times, and has also amplified the risk of cancer inclusive of colorectal, breast, liver, pancreatic, endometrial cancer (Nithya et al., 2023). Acute hyperglycemia may result in life threatening conditions like non-ketotic hyperosmolar syndrome and ketoacidosis (Victor et al., 2022).

Diabetes can be prevented by eating healthy diet, controlling lipids and blood pressure, regular exercise and avoiding smoking (Samuel et al., 2024). Numerous remedies including; daily exercise, dietary modifications and drugs having diverse mechanisms of action are suggested for treating the diabetes. Complementary and alternative remedies become an alternative approach for healthcare practitioners and patients for controlling the diabetes (Sharma et al., 2022).

DM has been cured with herbal drugs, and recent research on traditional anti-diabetic plants has unveiled the hypoglycemic potential of herbs. Vegetables and fruits enriched with phytochemicals are accepted to decrease the rate of starch digestion, making them valuable in treating after-meal hyperglycemia (Alam et al., 2022; Sivakumar & Deepa, 2023). Moreover, nutraceuticals of plant origin enriched with anti-diabetic phytochemicals are being paid a lot of attention to find new drugs to cure diabetes (Dinda & Dinda, 2022).

Galega officinalis L. (*Fabaceae*) was the first remedial plant described to have a strong anti-diabetic action and has been used to treat DM since the Middle Age (ANJORIN, 2023). Galegine, a guanidine derivative, structurally similar to metformin (anti-diabetic drug) was isolated from this plant, and is responsible for its anti-hyperglycemic action. The chemical structures of galegine and metformin are as under:

(Rios *et. al.*, 2015).

2. Literature Review

2.1 Taxonomical description

Phylum	:	Angiospermae
Sub-phylum	:	Dicotyledonae
Division	:	Lignosae
Order	:	Myrtales
Family	:	<i>Punicaceae / Lythraceae</i>
Genus	:	<i>Punica</i>
Species	:	<i>Punica granatum</i> (Linn.)

(Sarkhosh *et al.*, 2021; Shilpa *et al.*, 2023)

2.1.1 Vernacular names

English	:	Wild pomegranate
Persian	:	Anaar
Arabic	:	Romman
French	:	Grenade
Spanish	:	Granada

(Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2020; Kushwaha *et al.*, 2020)

2.2 Botanical description

The generic name, *Punica*, comes from the Roman name of Carthage, a place historically famous for growing the best pomegranates. Pomegranate literally means seeded (“*granatus*”) apple (“*pomum*”) (Safavi, 2014). Pomegranate (*Punica granatum*) is a tree, usually 12 to 16 feet in height with many

spiny branches (Ashrafi *et al.*, 2023; Khan *et al.*, 2020), which owing to acclimatize to unsympathetic natural setting has the capability to grow in dry and barren conditions (Vadivel *et al.*, 2024). The pomegranate plant is narrated in the divine Quran as a plant from paradise and has been declared twice as a premium creation of Allah Almighty.

Fig. 1.1 A pomegranate tree loaded with fruit

Fig. 1.2 Pomegranate Fruit and seeds

2.3 Traditional and medicinal uses

In addition to being used as fruit, pomegranate has been mentioned as a leading remedy even in ancient literature as described by Hippocrates, Soranus, Pliny and Dioscorides. Owing to its huge therapeutic potential, pomegranate has been designated as “super food”. Recently, research is being carried on the prebiotic application of pomegranates (Dardona, 2023), and pomegranate is being designated as the “elixir of youth” (Fahmy & Farag, 2022).

Pomegranate has been used as an important herbal drug in traditional medicine for centuries (Ranjha et al., 2021). The fruit is used for the treatment of microbial infections, dysentery, diarrhea, hemorrhage, acidosis, helminthiasis and pathologies of respiratory tract (Abdelkarim et al., 2023; Rodríguez González et al., 2020). The dried peel (rind) extract finds many applications in folk medicine like colitis, stomach-ache, anthelmintic, cardio-tonic, diuretic, astringent (Shaikh & Ahmed, 2021). The fruit rind ground in water is drunk every morning by the diabetics. The fruit of pomegranate is used with the juice of *Cynodon dactylon* to treat cold and runny nose. The juice of pomegranate flower is used for treating nose bleeds. The seed decoction is used for treating syphilis. Juice of seeds and the whole fruit helps in treating diarrhea and jaundice (Ge et al., 2021; Rezapour et al., 2023) The sour sauce of pomegranate is commonly used for many dishes

and salads. The colored arils of pomegranate give a luscious juice (Kamış et al., 2022).

2.4 Phytochemical constituents

The remedial effects shown by *Punica granatum* are because of the presence of particular phytochemical constituents. The principal phytochemicals are polyphenols which mainly include flavonoids (catechins, anthocyanins and other complex flavonoids) as well as hydrolysable tannins (ellagic and gallagic acid esters of glucose, punicalagin, punicalin, pendunculagin), which are responsible for 92% of antioxidant action. Punicalagins (one of the ellagitannins present in the outer portion of the fruit) having two anomers punicalagin A & B, are responsible for more than 50% antioxidant potential of pomegranate juice (Fraschetti et al., 2023).

The edible portion of *Punica granatum* fruit is enriched with sugars, polysaccharides, acids, polyphenols, vitamins, essential minerals (Magangana et al., 2020; Valero-Mendoza et al., 2023) and several anti-oxidants (ellagic acid, ellagitannins, punicalin, punicalagin and anthocyanins) (Olvera-Sandoval et al., 2022).

Phytochemical investigation reveals the presence of ellagic acid, ascorbic acid, punicalic acid, caffeic acid, sterols, quercetin, catechin, Epigallocatechingallate (EGCG), phenolic punicalagins, anthocyanins and flavonoids. The seed oil mainly contains punicalic acid (95%) along with ilagic acid, sterols and ellagic acid while the juice of the pulp

has high amounts of iron, anthocyanins, EGCG and ascorbic acid. The leaves are highly enriched with flavone glycosides (luteolin, aspigenin) and tannins (punicafolin, punicalin). The peel (rind) is reported to have flavonols, flavonones, flavones, EGCG, anthocyanidins, Rutin, phenolic punicalagins, quercetin, gallic acid and fatty acids (Saparbekova et al., 2023).

2.5 Mineral content

Minerals play vital role in the production of secondary metabolites (responsible for remedial effects of healing plants). Elemental investigation of *Punica granatum* revealed the concentration of ten minerals is as follows; Potassium (55.19 mg/L), Sodium (1.279 mg/L), Magnesium (3.721 mg/L), Calcium (1.650 mg/L), Zinc (0.430 mg/L), Iron (0.466 mg/L), Manganese (0.033 mg/L), Lead (1.119 mg/L), Copper (0.231 mg/L) and Cobalt (0.031 mg/L). These elements are responsible for treating various diseased states. The concentration of Potassium was found to be the highest while the concentration of Cobalt is the lowest (Dichala et al., 2021).

2.6 Physicochemical Analysis

Punica granatum is reported to have ash values as total ash (4.4% w/w), acid-insoluble ash (0.9% w/w), water-soluble ash (2.82% w/w). Extractive values as alcoholic (19.23% w/w) and aqueous (28.16% w/w) were calculated. Loss on drying (LOD) value (12.15% w/w) was recorded (Meena et al., 2021; Tarantino et al., 2022)

2.7 Pharmacological activities

Pomegranate has wide-ranging potential therapeutic applications including cancer prevention, dental problems, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes as well as protection against ultra-violet (UV) radiations. Some other applications include male infertility, infant brain ischemia, obesity, arthritis and Alzheimer's disease (Bhandary et al., 2012). Literature reports various pharmacological actions of *Punica granatum* including anti-cancer, antioxidant, anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory and anti-septic effects (Regolo et al., 2024). The pomegranate has anti-atherosclerotic, anti-viral, anti-oxidant and anti-

bacterial actions (Wianowska & Olszowy-Tomczyk, 2023). *Punica granatum* has also been used to treat erectile dysfunction as well as to protect against ultraviolet (UV) rays-induced skin injuries and infections (Harwansh & Deshmukh, 2024).

Punica granatum due to its anti-microbial and anti-oxidant actions is an important herbal drug to treat various diseased states (Güner & Aşkun, 2023). Pomegranate has also been used successfully to cure the relatively resistant infections cause by *E. coli*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus epidermidis*. The pomegranate peel has anti-microbial action. The extract of pomegranate leaves has been used as astringent (for dysentery and diarrhea) as well as it finds application as eye wash. Pomegranate methanolic extract has been investigated for possible anthelmintic potential (against *Pheretima posthuma*, the Indian earthworm) in concentration 50, 100 and 150 mg/ml (Ahmed et al., 2023).

Pomegranate owing to its phytochemicals shows anti-cancer potential (by inhibiting growth of cancerous cells) against numerous types of cancer. Pomegranate juice is reported to have anti-atherosclerotic, chemo-therapeutic, anti-inflammatory and chemo-preventive role. The juice has been shown to have high antioxidant action and is found efficacious in preventing platelet aggregation, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation, atherosclerosis and several other cardiovascular ailments (Lorzadeh et al., 2022; Stefanou et al., 2021)

Punicic acid (major constituent of pomegranate oil) is considered an anti-cancer agent and oil consumption inhibits prostate cancer invasion in human. The research reports that punicic acid reduces apo-lipoprotein B100 (apoB) secretion and thus lowers the risk of coronary artery disease (CAD) and atherosclerosis (Johari et al., 2022).

Pomegranate oil is noted to lower the total cholesterol and recognized sex steroids from the oil are proposed to be a good alternative therapy for hormonal replacement therapy (HRT) in women during menopause. The polysterols and polyphenols present in pomegranate oil are helpful in preventing wrinkle-formation, wound healing, tempering the inflammatory responses,

alleviating inflamed skin and reducing redness. Pomegranate fruit contains substantial amount of vitamins, anthocyanins, polyphenols, polysaccharides, minerals and acids. The fruit (edible portion) is usually consumed fresh but may also be processed into canned beverages, jams, juice, jellies, syrup, food supplements, pomegranate wine (grenadine), colorant and flavorant (Adel-Mehraban et al., 2022; Bayati & Asadi-Gharneh, 2020; Yang et al., 2023). The fruit finds its application as flavoring and coloring agent (dye) in healthcare, beauty products (creams, shampoos) and handcrafted items (fancy carpets) (Kandyliis & Kokkinomagoulos, 2020). The high polyphenolic content of pomegranate makes it an excellent anti-oxidant herb with most of the anti-oxidant activity in the rind of the fruit (Salim et al., 2020). The pulp of fruit and seed are stomachic. The bark of stem and root shows anthelmintic and astringent actions (Hassani Moghaddam & Sepahvand, 2020).

3. Aims and Objectives

The aim of this study is to investigate scientifically the anti-cancer effect on HepG2 cell line and *in vitro* anti-diabetic effect by using different extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*.

4. Material & Method

4.1 Plant Material

In September-October 2016, about 12-kilogram fresh leaves of *Punica granatum* were collected from the botanical garden of Government College University, Lahore, Pakistan situated adjacent to Lahore Zoo at the Mall Road, Lahore. The plant was authenticated from Herbarium of Department of Botany, Government College University, Lahore, Pakistan, and a voucher number GC. Herb. Bot. 3324 dated 02-11-2016 was issued for the plant. Leaves were cleaned with water and dried under shade for 5 weeks. Dried leaves were crumbled in colloidal mill, retained in oven for 3 days, then comminuted and kept in a tightly-closed bottle.s

4.2 Chemicals and solvents

All the solvents and chemicals employed were of analytical scale.

4.3 Analytical Study Methods For Plant leave *Punica granatum*

4.3.1 Extraction

4.3.1.1 Hot Extraction

Sixty gram powder of *Punica granatum* leaves was subjected to sequential hot extraction with n-hexane, chloroform and methanol. The powdered material was put in a filter paper to make a thimble, then it was placed in thimble assemblage and 3 liters of solvent added to the round bottom flask of soxhlet apparatus. At the end of extraction, the extracts were concentrated in rotary evaporator at a temperature lower than boiling point of the solvent, till the extracts become semi-solid in consistency. Then, the extracts were transferred to air-tight vials and placed in an oven (at 25°C) till completely dry. Then, the percentage yield was calculated in relation to the initial quantity of powdered material taken.

4.3.1.2 Cold Extraction

Twenty-five-gram powder of *Punica granatum* leaves was taken in a beaker (1000 ml) and 250 ml of ethanol was added. Then, beaker was stirred with magnetic stirrer for 24 hours at 50 rpm and sifted through a filter paper. After collecting the filtrate, ethanol (another 250 ml) was added to the residue and stirred with magnetic stirrer for one hour, then filtered and collected the filtrate. The method was repeated twice, and the extracts were dried to semi-solid state in rotary evaporator. Applied the same methodology for aqueous extraction and collected the resultant extract in rotary evaporator (connected to ultra-low chiller having a temperature of 4 °C) at 60-65 °C heating water bath temperature.

4.3.2 Physicochemical Analysis

Physicochemical investigation was done according to the methods illustrated in (Usp & Volume, 2005).

4.3.2.1 Moisture content

Two gram of powdered leaves was taken in a washed, dried, weighed and tarred silica crucible and placed in oven for 30 Min at 105 °C. Repeated the procedure and noted the weight of crucible (with powder) after every 30 Min till the weight

becomes constant. Then, crucible was cooled in desiccator and determined the loss in weight by deducting the weight of powdered leaves from that of the silica crucible. Moisture content specifies

the percent of dry powder and was calculated by using the equations given below (Usp & Volume, 2005).

$$\text{Dry matter (\%)} = \frac{\text{weight of dried sample}}{\text{weight of sample before drying}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Moisture content (\%)} = 100 - \text{Dry Matter (\%)}$$

4.3.2.2 Ash Values

Ash values include total ash, sulfated ash, acid insoluble ash, acid soluble ash, water insoluble ash and water-soluble ash (Usp & Volume, 2005).

4.3.2.3 Extractive values

Extractive values include acid-soluble and water-soluble extractive values and were determined by using methods illustrated in (Usp & Volume, 2005).

4.3.3 Estimation of Primary Metabolites

4.3.3.1 Total Proteins

Total protein content was estimated by the way as specified by (Lowry et al., 1951). For this purpose, one-gram powder of *Punica granatum* leaves was put in a centrifuge tube. Then, 10 ml distilled water was added along with 5 drops of Triton-X, mixed well and kept for half an hour with intermittent agitation. After that, the tube was centrifuged for 10 Min at 2700 rpm and collected the supernatant. Later on, 100 µl of the supernatant was put in a test tube and using distilled water volume was made up to 1 ml. Three ml of Reagent-C (prepared by blending 50 ml of Reagent A (2% Na₂CO₃ in 0.1 N NaOH) and 1 ml of Reagent B (0.5% CuSO₄ in 1% potassium sodium tartarate) and 0.2 ml of folin-ciocalteau's reagent was added. Then, test tube was placed at room temperature for half an hour. Blank contained all the reagents but no sample powder. Bovine serum albumin (BSA) standard, treated same as the sample, was used in a range of 12.5-100 µg/ml to make the standard curve. Then absorbance was taken at 600 nm against blank.

The same methodology was adopted for protein estimation in extracts and powdered leaf material of pomegranate.

4.3.3.2 Total Lipids

Total lipids were quantified by the method described by (Besbes et al., 2004). Sixty five gram of powdered leaf material in a neat, weighed and tarred round bottom flask. The sample was extracted with n-hexane (500 ml) in soxhlet apparatus. Rotary evaporator was used to dry the extract and total lipid content was determined by subtracting the weight of dried extract to that weight of the round bottom flask.

4.3.3.3 Total Carbohydrates

The total carbohydrates were estimated by using formula stated by (Al-Hooti et al., 1997) as given under;

$$\text{Total carbohydrates (\%)} = 100 - [\text{total proteins} + \text{total ash} + \text{total fat} + \text{total moisture}]$$

4.3.4 Estimation of Secondary Metabolites

4.3.4.1 Total Polysaccharides

Total polysaccharides were estimated by method described by (Hussain et al., 2008). For this purpose, extract (200 mg) was put in a centrifuge tube, and to eliminate soluble carbohydrates (sugars) present, it was mixed with 80% hot ethanol (7 ml) for 2 Min using vortex mixer, and hereafter it was centrifuged for 10 Min at 2700 rpm. Then, anthrone reagent addition developed green coloration. The same methodology was adopted repetitively till residue did not develop color upon the addition of anthrone reagent. Water bath was used to dry the final residue. Then, distilled water and HCl (25%) were intermixed in 1:1 (v/v) ratio, and extracted the dried material with this mixture for 20 Min at 0 °C, and then centrifuged for 10 Min at 2700 rpm. Extraction was repeated twice following the same methodology, and collected all the supernatants in a volumetric flask, then made up the volume 100

ml with distilled water. An aliquot (0.1 ml) of this diluted supernatant was put in a test tube and volume was made 1 ml with distilled water and added 4 ml of anthrone agent. Then, it was heated for 8 Min on water bath. After that, the mixture was cooled and measured the absorbance (intensity of green color) at 630 nm against blank. Blank contained all the reagents except the extract and was treated the same as samples. Glucose solution being used as a standard was prepared as stock solution having a concentration of 1mg/ml and further diluted to prepare a range of concentrations; 20, 40, 60, 100 and 200 µl/ml, treated the same as sample, was used to draw standard curve. The values obtained were multiplied with 0.9 to determine the total

polysaccharide content.

4.3.4.2 Total Glycosaponins

Total polysaccharides were quantified by a slightly modified method as described by (Hussain et al., 2008). For glycosaponin estimation, refluxed 1 gram of each extract for 30 Min with ethanol (50 ml) and collected the extract. Repeated the same procedure thrice and collected all the extracts, and then dried extracts to 10 ml in rotary evaporator. Acetone (50 ml) was taken in a tarred beaker, the extract was poured down drop-wise, which resulted in the formation of precipitates. Dried the precipitates at 100 °C in an oven and weighed. Then, the following formula gave the percent total glycosaponins.

$$\text{Total glycosaponins (\%)} = \frac{\text{weight of precipitate}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times 100$$

4.3.4.3 Total Polyphenols

Total polyphenolic content was determined by applying the formula illustrated by (Slinkard & Singleton, 1977). Extract and Gallic acid stock solution having a concentration 1mg/ml was prepared in methanol. Then, further dilutions of both (Extract and Gallic acid) were prepared by diluting 20, 40, 80 and 120 µl of stock solution up to 1000 µl with methanol. A volume of 200 µl was taken from each dilution, added folin-ciocalteau's (FC) reagent (200µl), 15% Na₂CO₃ (1ml), then made up the volume up to 3 ml with methanol. Blank was prepared by adding 200µl of methanol in place of extract. All of the solutions were incubated at room temperature for 90 Min. Then measured the absorbance at 760 nm against blank, drawn the standard curve, and determined total polyphenolic content (expressed as mg of Gallic acid per gram of extract) from the standard curve.

methanol. Then, 200 µg/ml from each conc. of quercetin and extract solution was taken and methanol was added to make up the volume 1 ml. Then 100 µl of each; 1M Potassium acetate and 10% Aluminum nitrate, and 4.6 ml of distilled water were added. Incubated all the solutions at room temperature for 45 Min, and measured absorbance at 415 nm against blank. Blank contained all the reagents but no standard/extract. Drawn the standard curve and total flavonoids (per mg of quercetin) were determined using linear regression.

4.3.4.4 Total Flavonoids

Total flavonoids were determined by method described by (Chang et al., 2002). Stock solution of quercetin (used as a standard) was prepared having a concentration of 1mg/ml and diluted further to prepare concentrations; 10, 20, 40, 80 and 120 µg/ml using methanol. Each extract was also prepared at 1mg/ml concentration with

4.3.5 Analytical Studies

4.3.5.1 Ultraviolet-visible profiling

Stock solutions of all extracts were prepared in methanol at a concentration of 1 mg/ml. To prepare working dilutions, 100 µl of stock solutions was taken in test tubes and made up the volume 10 ml with methanol. Then, analyzed all the sample dilutions at 800-200 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer against blank and recorded the results.

4.3.5.2 Fourier transform infra-red (FTIR) spectroscopy profiling

Weighed one gram of powdered leaves and placed in pestle and mortar to reduce its particle size.

After size reduction, 100 mg of KBr was mixed scrupulously in it and prepared the disc pellets using a hydraulic press. FTIR spectrum, in mid-range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} was obtained for the disc pellets.

4.3.5.3 Mineral estimation through Atomic absorption spectrophotometer

The method illustrated by was adopted for mineral estimation. After cleaning the volumetric flask with nitric acid (20 % w/v), the flasks were rinsed using de-ionized water. One gram of powdered leaves was put in a flask and added the digestion mixture (prepared by mixing 1 ml of hydrochloric acid and 15 ml of nitric acid in a ratio of 1:3) to the flask. Then, flask was heated under a fuming hood till the brown fumes seized. The material was decolorized by adding hydrogen peroxide drop-wise and then cooled. Then, it was filtered using a whatmann filter paper no. 2 to remove any visible particulate matter, and made up the volume 100 ml with de-ionized water. From standard solutions (1000 ppm), working standard solutions having a range of concentrations; 0, 1, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 100 ppm were prepared, and then analyzed with atomic absorption spectrophotometer for mineral estimation. The analysis was repeated in triplicate. Standard curve was drawn and linear regression equation was obtained. From linear regression equation concentrations were calculated and recorded.

4.4 Method For Analysis of Anti-Tumor Activity

4.4.1 Cell line

HepG2 cell culture was provided by Centre of Excellence in Molecular Biology (CEMB), University of the Punjab, Lahore.

4.4.2 3-(4,5-dimethylthiazole-2-yl)-2,5 diphenyl tetrazolium Assay

The method illustrated by (Khairunnisa & Karthik, 2014) was adopted with slight modifications for performing MTT assay. Media containing DMEM, 1% pen./strep. and 10% FBS was prepared in a 50 ml falcon tube. Cryopreserved hepatoma (Hep-G2) cell line was thawed at 37 °C in a water bath. Then, cells were

plated in a T25 flask having media (20 ml) and softly agitated. The cells were then incubated for 24 hour at 37 °C / 95% relative humidity / 5% CO_2 . When cells became confluent, these were trypsinized (6 ml media + 3 ml trypsin), and then centrifuged for 5 Min at 4000 rpm. Aliquot was removed and cell pellet obtained was re-suspended in media. Cell count was done by adding 10 μl of cell suspension on haemocytometer. Then, cells were plated in a 96-well micro-titer plate (2000 cells/well) and incubated at 37 °C overnight. Henceforth, extracts (ethanol, methanol, chloroform) were prepared at concentrations; 50, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and added to wells and incubated again for 24 hour, each concentration was plated in triplicate. To each well, 20 μl MTT reagent (5 mg/ml) was added, then placed in incubator at 37 °C / 95% relative humidity / 5% CO_2 for 4 hour. After removing 80% of the cell media having MTT reagent with micropipette, 150 μl of DMSO was introduced to each well. ELISA plate reader was used to observe the cell viability at 590 nm.

4.5 Methods For Analysis of Anti-Diabetic Activity

To analyze the anti-diabetic activity of various extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*, *in vitro* anti-diabetic models like α -amylase and glucose uptake by yeast cell were employed.

4.5.1 Alpha-amylase inhibition assay

Alpha-amylase assay was performed through the procedure modified from (Apostolidis et al., 2007). To carry out the procedure, 5 mg/ml of sample stock solution was prepared by dissolving extracts in methanol. One ml of this stock solution was taken in the test tube upon which 1 ml of α -amylase (1% w/v suspension prepared by dissolving 0.5 gram of alpha-amylase in 50 ml of Sodium phosphate buffer having a pH of 6.9) was added. The resultant mixture was then incubated for 5-15 min at 37°C. After the initial incubation, 1 ml starch solution was added and incubated again for 15 min. A mixture containing 1 ml of sample and 3 ml of the buffer was prepared to be used as sample blank. One ml of 3,5-di-nitrosalicylic acid (DNSA), the coloring reagent was then added. The mixture was kept at 85°C in a

thermoregulatory bath for 15 min. Afterwards, the mixture was cooled down to room temperature and measured the absorbance at 540 nm with UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Standard drug was

acarbose, for which same procedure was adopted except for addition of sample solution. To calculate percentage inhibition, following equation was used:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Abs. Control} - \text{Abs. Sample})}{\text{Abs. Control}} \times 100$$

Anti-diabetic potential of all extracts was examined.

4.5.2 Glucose uptake by yeast cells

4.5.2.1 Preparation of yeast cells

Method described by (Faiyaz Ahmed et al., 2009) was adopted with fewer modifications for preparing yeast cell suspension. Commercially available baker's yeast was repeatedly centrifuged in distilled water for 5 min at 3000 rpm to wash it thoroughly till the supernatant becomes clear. The 10% (v/v) yeast suspension in distilled water was prepared (Faiyaz Ahmed et al., 2009).

mg/ml and 1 ml of each extract was supplemented with 1 ml of glucose solution having conc. 5 mM, then incubated for 10 min at 37 °C. At the end of this pre-incubation, 100 µL of yeast suspension (10%) was introduced to the mixtures in order to start the reaction and was incubated again for 1 hour at 37 °C, after that, centrifuged the reaction mixture for 5 min at 2500 rpm. The supernatant collected was used to investigate the glucose conc. with UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 620 nm. Control was prepared by replacing the extract with distilled water and was treated the same as the extracts. Metronidazole was used as a standard drug, while distilled water was the blank. Then, following equation helped to calculate the percentage inhibition:

4.5.3 Glucose uptake by yeast cells assay

For the investigation of glucose uptake by yeast cells, method described by was (Gupta et al., 2012) adapted with some modifications. Extract solutions were prepared having concentration 5

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Abs. Control} - \text{Abs. Sample})}{\text{Abs. Control}} \times 100$$

5. Results and discussion

5.1 Percentage yields of extracts

The percentage yields of extracts obtained from cold and hot extraction are tabulated as (Table 2.1):

Table 2.1 Percentage yields of extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*

Sr. No.	Name of extract	Percentage yield (% w/w)
1	n-Hexane	7.17
2	Chloroform	3.68
3	Methanol	28.53
4	Ethanol	32.69
5	Distilled water	5.20

5.2 Physicochemical Analysis

The results of physicochemical analysis on powder of leaves of *Punica granatum* are given under (Table 2.2):

Table 2.2 Physicochemical analysis of powder of leaves of *Punica granatum*

Sr. No.	Physicochemical properties	Percentage contents (% w/w)
1	Moisture content	7.25
2	Total Ash	9.436
3	Water soluble ash	2.61
4	Acid insoluble ash	0.53
5	Sulfated ash	20.34
6	Water soluble extractive value	10
7	Alcohol soluble extractive value	8

Moisture content is an indicative of stability of extracts, herbal products and powders and it should be at minimum as it helps in chemical breakdown and microbial contamination. It is helpful to test non-volatile substances present. Ash test is applicable on powdered therapeutic substances and its value helps in detection of the purity and quality of the drugs. Similarly, carbon free ash indicates the presence of silicates, phosphates and carbonates and is helpful for drug analysis. Water and Alcohol soluble extractive values directly detect the polar compounds (glycosides, phenols, tannins) present in the drugs (Venkatesham et al., 2021).

Ash values reflect inorganic content (metallic salts, silica) of herbal products and may be detrimental to human health. Extractive values, depending upon the polarity of the solvent involved, indicate polar and non-polar nature of herbal constituents (Amalraj et al., 2022). Extractive values of water and alcohol (polar solvents) computes polar integrants (phenols, glycosides, tannins) of herbals (Sultana et al., 2023).

5.3 Estimation of primary metabolites

The total lipids, total carbohydrates and total proteins present in the powdered leaves of *Punica granatum* are as follows (Table 2.3):

Table 2.3 Estimation of primary metabolites present in powdered leaves of *Punica granatum*

Sr. No.	Primary metabolites	Percentage contents \pm S.D. (% w/w)
1	Total lipids	5.420 \pm 0.08
2	Total carbohydrates	52.82 \pm 0.06
3	Total proteins	25.07 \pm 0.05

Primary metabolites play vital role as far as the metabolic activities and growth is concerned, while secondary metabolites (terpenes, sterols, essential oils, tannins, alkaloids, phenols) show specific activities and do not play any role in metabolism (Salam et al., 2023).

The primary metabolites values assess the nutritional importance of leaves of *Punica granatum*. The total lipids content indicates the

presence of carotenoids, extracted with n-Hexane (non-polar solvent) (Alves et al., 2021).

5.4 Estimation of secondary metabolites

Total flavonoids, total polysaccharides, total polyphenols, total proteins and total glycosaponins in the extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* are as under (Table 2.4):

Table 2.4 Estimation of secondary metabolites of extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*

Extract	Total polyphenols	Total glycosaponins	Total flavonoids	Total polysaccharides	Total proteins
n-Hexane	32.7±0.24	31.24±0.07	161.7±0.47	8.3±0.06	80.0±1.63
Chloroform	43.4±0.12	47.31±0.18	118.3±0.94	7.3±0.06	238.3±1.25
Methanol	55.2±0.41	82.41±0.39	215.7±0.47	9.2±0.05	782.7±0.94
Distilled water	41.8±0.31	69.67±0.37	47.7±1.25	6.7±0.08	835.2±0.47
Ethanol	84.7±0.21	53.9±0.12	335.0±0.82	8.7±0.07	429.0±1.41

After drawing the standard curve, regression equation was obtained for each test, as for flavonoids ($y=0.001+0.022x$, $R^2=0.961$), for total polyphenols ($y=0.004x+0.018$, $R^2=0.994$), for total polysaccharides ($y=0.026x-0.013$, $R^2=0.990$) and for total proteins ($y = 0.001x-0.003$, $R^2=0.990$).

As polysaccharides are insoluble in water, so aqueous extract showed the least value of polysaccharides, while Ethanolic and Methanolic extracts, due to structural characteristics showed high polysaccharide contents (Benslimane et al., 2020). Methanolic extract contained the highest glycosaponin content while n-Hexane extract contained the least. Literature reports various therapeutic effects of glycosaponins such as anti-hypercholesterolemic, anti-hyperglycemic, hepatoprotective and also anti-tumor potential by inducing apoptosis and inhibiting cellular growth (Maphetu et al., 2022).

Ethanolic and Methanolic extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* showed the highest total flavonoid and polyphenolic content. Polyphenols have protective effect in various diseases due to their antioxidant action (Saparbekova et al., 2023). Dietary elements rich in polyphenolic content have protective action against aging, heart & blood vessel diseases and cancer as well (Rudrapal et al., 2022).

n-Hexane extracts contained the least quantity of total flavonoids while Ethanolic and Methanolic

extracts were detected to have the highest total flavonoid content. Flavonoids are reported to show anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, anti-viral, anti-fungal as well as anticancer effects (Ngibad et al., 2023) (Maphetu et al., 2022).

The secondary metabolites impart the plant its specific therapeutic potential and medicinal value (Twaij & Hasan, 2022). Secondary metabolites are formed by chemical modification of primary metabolites (Bhatla & Lal, 2023). Glycosaponins, non-nitrogenous, toxic compounds are valuable in cancer, hyper-cholesterolemic conditions and are cardio-active. Glycosides, natural cardio-stimulants are valuable in the treatment of heart problems like congestive heart failure (CHF) and cardiac arrhythmia. Tannins and flavonoids belong to phenolic compounds which mainly act as anti-oxidants (Zanzabil et al., 2023). Flavonoids are active against viruses, inflammation, cancer, and also inhibit DNA oxidation and cell proliferation, increase apoptosis rate and are antioxidant (Slika et al., 2022).

5.5 Ultraviolet-visible profiling

UV-visible spectroscopy is a highly valuable technique to qualitatively analyze the unknown substances. Samples were prepared at 100 µg/ml conc. and scanned with uv-visible spectrophotometer. The overlay scan is represented in Fig. 2.1

Figure 2.1 UV-Visible profile of different extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*

π bonds (unsaturation) are responsible for absorption in uv-visible region. Hence, chromophore is a molecular group having π bond. If introduced in organic compounds, it results in a new compound with absorption between 185 to 1000 nm. If conjugation is extended by coupling conjugated systems, the wavelength and the intensity of absorption is increased. Transition metal ions also show absorbance between 400-700 nm because of the presence of electronic energy levels (Pareek & Jaswal, 2024).

UV-visible data helps in detection of solvophilicity (hydrophilic and lipophilic nature) of herbal ingredients (Hussain et al., 2021), while FTIR helps in their identification (Brangule et al., 2020; Upton et al., 2020)

From this study, not only the conjugate systems can be identified but it is also helpful for

comparative studies. All samples showed broader peaks in 200-400 nm region and smaller, narrow peaks in 400-800 nm region. The absorption of UV-Visible radiations between 200-400 nm indicates the presence of more than one conjugates systems/ring systems as benzene, anthraquinones and naphthalene absorb in this region.

5.6 Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy

FTIR spectroscopy showed various types of functional groups present in the powder and extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*. FTIR spectra are as under:

Fig. 2.2 FTIR spectrum of powdered leaves of *Punica granatum*

Fig. 2.3 FTIR spectrum of n-hexane extract of leaves of *Punica granatum*

Fig. 2.4 FTIR spectrum of chloroform extract of leaves of *Punica granatum*

Fig. 2.5 FTIR spectrum of methanol extract of leaves of *Punica granatum*

Fig. 2.6 FTIR spectrum of distilled water extract of leaves of *Punica granatum*

Fig. 2.7 FTIR spectrum of ethanol extract of leaves of *Punica granatum*

FTIR vibrations helped in functional groups identification. C-H bonds from isoprenoids show bending vibrations in Area 1 ($<1000\text{cm}^{-1}$) while C-

O bonds show stretching vibrations in Area 2 ($1000-1130\text{cm}^{-1}$). O-H and C-O bending in esters occurs in Area 3 ($1150-1270\text{cm}^{-1}$) whereas Area 4

(1300-1450 cm^{-1}) represents C-O and C-C from amide and phenyl functional groups respectively. Aromatic domains and bending vibrations of N-H are represented in Area 5 (1500-1600 cm^{-1}). C=O stretching vibrations in esters, ketones, aldehydes, glycerides and fatty acids and N-H bending vibrations in amino acids correspond to Area 6 (1600-2200 cm^{-1}). C-H bond stretching vibrations of $-\text{CH}_3$, $-\text{CH}_2$ from methoxy compounds and lipids and also aldehydes including cis double bonds corresponds to Area 7 (2800-3000 cm^{-1}). O-H stretching vibrations in water, carbohydrates, phenols, amides and alcohols are represented by Area 8 (3200-3600 cm^{-1}) (Guerrero-Pérez & Patience, 2020).

FTIR scans of n-hexane, chloroform and ethanol extracts were found similar indicating the presence of compounds with similar functional groups. Likewise, FTIR scans of methanol extract and distilled water extract were alike.

5.7 Mineral Estimation through atomic absorption spectrophotometer

Calcium, chromium, copper, iron, magnesium, manganese, nickel, potassium, sodium and zinc were analyzed with atomic absorption spectrophotometer in various extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* and results were tabulated as follows:

Table 2.5 Mineral content estimation of extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*

Element/Mineral	n-Hexane extract (mg/L)	Chloroform extract	Ethanol extract
Magnesium (Mg)	* N.D.	4.5	35.2
Iron (Fe)	16.5	11.5	10.5
Copper (Cu)	0.75	0.5	1.0
Chromium (Cr)	0.75	1.0	2.0
Zinc (Zn)	17.1	20.2	22.5
Manganese (Mn)	23.3	28.6	34.4
Sodium (Na)	7.5	10.0	140.0
Potassium (K)	5.0	12.5	442.5
Nickel (Ni)	* N.D.	* N.D.	* N.D.
Calcium (Ca)	* N.D.	* N.D.	* N.D.

* N.D. = Not determined.

Minerals have two basic types; micro-nutrients and macro-nutrients, and are needed for proper growth and functioning of human body. Mineral deficiencies may disturb metabolic processes leading to various diseased states (acute and chronic), therefore, mineral supplements are being used globally for combating mineral deficiencies (Hoque et al., 2023). Herbal products are natural and cost-effective source of minerals and hold adequate amount of minerals for human health (Ganguly & Kumar, 2024).

Minerals play vital role in preventing and treating various pathological states. The elements can be exploited for their preventive remedial effects.

Sodium (Na) contributes in the transport of glucose and amino acids into the cells and energy production. Potassium (K) helps in maintaining

the heart rhythm and lowering the hypertension. Potassium takes part in various important metabolic reactions and its deficiency and excess can influence human health. Calcium (Ca) helps in overcoming various health issues like colon cancer, myocardial infarction, hypertension, premenstrual syndrome and reduces the risk of osteoporosis by keeping the bones strong. Magnesium (Mg) provides protection against diabetes and its related complications by improving insulin sensitivity. It also reduces hypertension. Copper (Cu) is important for preventing inflammation, treating chest wounds, arthritis and analogous ailments. Zinc (Zn) deficiency may result in hair loss, arrested sexual maturation, delayed wound healing, growth retardation and emotional disturbance. Iron (Fe)

is an essential mineral for the prevention of anemia and cough associated with the use of angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors. Manganese (Mn) plays important role in protein metabolism and also helps the diabetics in metabolizing carbohydrates, hence is also helpful to treat diabetes. Lead (Pb) is a non-essential element, toxic in nature because it is responsible for brain and kidney damage, rise in blood pressure, diminished learning abilities by disruption of nervous system, miscarriages and subtle abortion and reduced fertility of men by damaging the sperms (Bibi et al., 2023). Chromium acts as a cofactor for insulin action (Genchi et al., 2021). The mineral content of the plants varies from plant to plant and region to region and is highly affected by various environmental factors like age of plant, soil conditions in which the plant grows, season of sample collection, atmosphere and pollution (Karahan et al., 2020).

Minerals like secondary metabolites play very important role and various pharmacological actions of curative plants are dependent upon the minerals present in that particular plant. Mineral estimation of five extracts of leaves of pomegranate showed that the leaves have high content of various minerals. Hence, the leaves of pomegranate can be used as an important source of several minerals to cure various mineral deficiency disorders as well as some other pathological conditions like anemia, arrhythmia, diabetes etc.

5.8 Anti-Tumor Activity Results and Discussion

The cytotoxicity of three extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* was evaluated by MTT assay at two different conc. (50 µg/ml and 100 µg/ml). The results are represented graphically in Fig. 3.1 and 3.2.

Figure 3.1 Comparison of DMSO group with n-Hexane, Chloroform and Ethanol extracts at 50 µg/ml concentration. Data was analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test. Values are cited as the mean \pm S.D; * = $p < 0.05$, *** = $p < 0.001$.

Figure 3.2 Comparison of DMSO group with n-Hexane, Chloroform and Ethanol extracts at 100 µg/ml concentration. Data was analyzed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test. Values are cited as the mean \pm S.D; * = $p < 0.05$, *** = $p < 0.001$

The results show that tested extracts have no inhibitory action on HepG2 cells. More interestingly, it is clear from the findings that chloroform extract and particularly ethanol extract significantly increased the HepG2 cell proliferation at 50 µg/ml concentration of sample extracts. While at 100 µg/ml concentration, only ethanol extract improved the cell proliferation appreciably.

In current study, the cytotoxic effects of three different extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* in human hepatoma (HepG2) cell line were tested which to the best of our knowledge is the first

report about the cytotoxic effect of leaves of pomegranate on HepG2 cancerous cell line. The results of present study clearly depict that tested extracts of pomegranate leaves have no inhibitory effect on HepG2 cancer cell line rather ethanol extract significantly increased the proliferation of HepG2 cells which indicate that certain phytochemicals may be present in ethanol extract of leaves of pomegranate that have growth-promoting effects on HepG2 cells so further investigation is required in this respect. The cytotoxic effect of these extracts still need to be tested on various other cancerous cell lines.

The effect of ethanol extract on cellular proliferation of HepG2 cell line may be due to hormesis. (Calabrese, 2004) defined the hormesis as a phenomenon described by any condition where exposure to a low concentration of a chemical substance or condition causes a favorable/stimulatory effect while exposure to a high concentration causes negative/inhibitory effect upon a cell or organism. A bi-phasic dose-response curve is the characteristic feature of hormesis (Calabrese, 2004). As reported (Kawata et al., 2009), silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) considerably enhanced the cellular viability which may be through hormesis (Kawata et al., 2009). The results may also be affected by too short exposure to cytotoxic substance present in the extracts as during MTT assay HepG2 cells were exposed to tested extracts for only 24 hours. The hypoxic environment also causes an increased proliferation of HepG2 cells. Hypoxia stimulates the cellular growth by inducing hexokinase-II (HK-II) expression and the inhibition of HK-II efficiently induces cellular death via apoptosis (Liu et al., 2023). Therefore, the effect of ethanol extract of pomegranate on growth of HepG2 cells may be partially explained based on these observations as reported by (Gwak et al., 2005) and ethanol extract may have some potential inducers for HK-II enzymes which requires further investigation. According to (Xu et al., 2013), miR-96 boosts the growth as well as migration of HepG2 cells (Xu et al., 2013). (Lv et al., 2014) described that E2F1 expression is related directly with the expression of H19, cellular proliferation

as well as invasion of HepG2 cells. E2F1 over-expression causes up-regulation of H19 expression and also stimulates cellular growth and invasion in HepG2 cells. And as the aflatoxin B1 (AFB1) could promote the H19 expression therefore, AFB1 triggers the growth and invasion in HepG2 cells. Hence, AFB1 has positive effect on HepG2 cells invasion and growth through H19 and E2F1 (Lv et al., 2014). Growth differentiation factor (GDF15) has the ability to enhance cellular viability, angiogenesis, migration and invasion of HepG2 cell line. Therefore, over-expression of GDF 15 might possibly increase the risk for hepato-cellular carcinoma (Xu, 2023). Whether the ethanol extract of pomegranate leaves causes increased cellular proliferation of HepG2 cell line by the mechanisms discussed above or some other mechanisms are involved, it is a matter that requires further investigation. The phytochemicals responsible for stimulating the HepG2 cell proliferation may be further investigated. Further, the cytotoxic action usually varies from cell line to cell line, hence the cytotoxic potential may also be tested on various other cell lines. The investigated extracts also need to be tested on primary cells for their proliferative/cytotoxic action.

5.9 Results for Anti-Diabetic Activity

α -Amylase inhibition assay: The percentage inhibition of α -amylase by various extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* and acarbose (standard drug) is represented graphically in Fig. 4.1

Figure 4.1 Percentage Alpha-amylase inhibition of various extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*. The data was analyzed using One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test to compare all the columns and values cited as the mean \pm S.D; * = $p < 0.05$, *** = $p < 0.001$

The potential α -amylase inhibition exhibited by various extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* ranged from 1.14% (methanol extract) to 84.22% (n-hexane extract). All the studied pomegranate extracts showed lesser α -amylase inhibition potential as compared to acarbose (72.81%) except n-hexane extract (84.22% α -amylase inhibition). α -Amylase inhibition activity of studied extracts was found to be in the following order: n-hexane extract (84.22%) > acarbose (72.81%) > ethanol extract (13.00%) > distilled water extract (4.46%) > chloroform extract (2.44%) > methanol extract (1.14%).

Herbal fractions with flavonoids and tannins show high α -Amylase inhibition (Kifle et al., 2021). Recent reports clearly describe the tannins as non-specific inhibitors of various hydrolytic-enzymes

like α -amylases, lipases, invertases and α -glucosidases. Glycosides found in the extracts are substrate for α -glucosidase and may inhibit the enzyme activity (Zhu et al., 2020). Alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins and terpenoids may be responsible for α -amylase inhibition (Babu et al., 2021; Shrestha et al., 2021). Tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids, phenols, saponins, and steroids of *Cassia absus* may be responsible for inhibition α -amylase activity (Navik et al., 2022; Sitaram et al., 2021). Phenolics that can form quinones (i.e chlorogenic acid, caffeic acid, gallic acid etc.) have more tendencies to react compared to phenolics which cannot form quinones. Semi-quinones could react with free thiol groups and amino-acid side chains of carbohydrate digesting enzymes. Previous report suggested that phenolic derivatives

of trypsin reduce the hydrolytic activity of enzymes. More interestingly, α -amylase inhibition is observed at optimum pH (6.9) of the enzyme which means that the herbals may inhibit the enzymatic activity even at physiological conditions. α -Amylase blockers from food phenolics are much safer and hence might be a favored alternative for inhibition of carbohydrate-hydrolyzing enzymes (Machado et al., 2024). Polysaccharides may improve glucose tolerance, reduce blood sugar level and increase serum insulin level and hence, may be beneficial for managing diabetes. Flavonoids also have hypoglycemic action (Sok Yen et al., 2021). Flavonoids (the most common phenols) are found abundantly in plants, especially in cells with photosynthetic function. All flavonoids show a basic $C_6-C_3-C_6$ nucleus and show various pharmacological actions like anti-diabetic, anti-viral, anti-allergic, anti-oxidant, hepato-protective and gastro-protective (Adhikari & Saha, 2023; Zhou et al., 2022). Bound phenolic extract shows greater α -amylase inhibition than free phenolic extract. It may be because bound phenolics are found usually as glycosides that's why show higher water-solubility compared to unbound phenolics which make aglycones. As enzymes function in aqueous environment, hence bound phenolics have the greater enzyme-inhibitor interaction than unbound phenolics. Nonetheless, both bound and free phenolics have inhibitory action on α -amylase and therefore reduce glucose absorption from gastro-intestinal tract (GIT) (Feng & Kong, 2022). Flavonoids and polyphenols obviously inhibit α -amylase and α -glucosidase. A positive relation is found between the total flavonoid and polyphenol content and

the capability of inhibition of these enzymes (Wu et al., 2020). Non-competitive inhibitors bind at allosteric site and alter V_{max} while K_m remains the same (Das et al., 2020). Natural polyphenols are described to inhibit the enzymes which hydrolyze carbohydrates (Ćorković et al., 2022). α -Amylase inhibition might be credited to several factors including; (1) direct adsorption of enzyme on fibers, (2) encapsulation of enzyme and starch by the fibers present in the sample extracts hence lowering the accessibility of starch to enzyme, (3) concentration of fibers, (4) presence of fiber blockers. All these factors collectively function to reduce α -Amylase enzymatic activity (Peddio et al., 2022). The plant extracts with high phenolic content show higher α -amylase inhibition. Recently, natural anti-oxidants as well as phenolics of plant origin are warranted for their lesser untoward effects (Semwal et al., 2023). n-Hexane extract shows the highest potential for α -amylase inhibition. Therefore, various secondary metabolites present in n-hexane extract of leaves of *Punica granatum* may be responsible for its α -amylase inhibitory action. Hence, the results of present study clearly furnish a healthy biochemical rationale for the use of *Punica granatum* as an alternative remedy in managing diabetes mellitus.

Glucose uptake by yeast cells assay: After treating with various extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*, glucose uptake into the yeast cells was found to enhance. Fig. 4.2 clearly portrays the % increase in glucose uptake by yeast cells at 5mM glucose concentration.

Figure 4.2 Percentage increase in glucose uptake by yeast cells shown by various extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum*. Data was analyzed by One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's test for comparing the columns and values cited as the mean \pm S.D; * = $p < 0.05$, *** = $p < 0.001$

It is evident from the results that all the extracts significantly increased the % glucose uptake in yeast cells though lower than the standard (metronidazole).

n-Hexane extract is found to exhibit the highest activity among all the extracts. Methanol and Ethanol extracts showed almost equal activity. The % increase in glucose uptake was found to be in the given order: metronidazole (75.63%) > n-hexane extract (55.06%) > methanol extract (46.17%) > ethanol extract (45.77%) > chloroform extract (34.50%) > distilled water extract (28.82%). The results evidently suggest that the extracts of leaves of pomegranate effectively increase the glucose uptake and in turn suggest that pomegranate has the capability of effectively increasing the glucose utilization hence, pomegranate leaves have anti-

diabetic potential. The results are in accordance with the already reported anti-diabetic potential of pomegranate.

Mechanism of glucose transportation across the plasma membrane of the yeast cell has been an attractive *in vitro* testing method for evaluating the anti-diabetic potential of herbs and various other compounds (Elbermawi et al., 2022). Recent research on the transport of some metabolizable glycosides and non-metabolizable sugars suggests that sugars are transported across the yeast plasma membrane via stereo-specific carriers present in the plasma membrane (Imieje et al., 2022; Lakache et al., 2022). Literature reported that glucose transport across yeast plasma (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) is exceptionally complex (Breedon & Tsukiyama, 2022; Qiu et al., 2023)

and the facilitated diffusion mode is generally agreed for glucose transport in yeast (Drew et al., 2021; Lao-Martil et al., 2023; Verhagen et al., 2023). Facilitated carriers/proteins specifically transport the solutes down the gradient meaning that glucose can only be effectively transported into the cells if the intracellular glucose is sufficiently low (Cherkas et al., 2020). The rate of glucose uptake by yeast cells is directly related to the extract concentration as well as extracellular glucose concentration, but saturation point ultimately seizes the relationship (Zainuddin et al., 2021). The glucose uptake assay was performed to investigate the activity of various extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* by using an *in vitro* model of yeast cells suspended in glucose solution (5 mM). The remaining glucose in the medium after a particular time period serves as an indicator of glucose uptake in this model (Sairam and Urooj, 2012; Woldemariam and Winkle, 2015). Type -II DM is basically the result of insulin deficiency which leads to hyperglycemia (Berbudi et al., 2020; Kumar et al., 2020; Solis-Herrera et al., 2021). Current study shows that all the tested extracts, compared to standard (metronidazole) significantly increased the glucose uptake by yeast cells (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) at a dose of 5 mg/ml.

6. Conclusion

Physicochemical tests were within limits. Total proteins, polyphenols, flavonoids, polysaccharides and glycosaponins were maximum present in distilled water extract, chloroform extract, ethanol extract, n-hexane extract and methanol extract respectively. The UV-Visible profile was found to be similar for chloroform extract, methanol extract, distilled water extract and ethanol extract. FTIR scan revealed the existence of numerous functional groups in the powdered leaves and extracts of pomegranate. Mineral analysis indicated the presence of high amounts of potassium, sodium, manganese, zinc and magnesium in ethanol extract compared to chloroform extract and n-hexane extract.

The findings of current study, clearly reveal that tested three extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* have no growth-inhibitory action on human HepG2 cancer cells rather tested extracts especially

ethanol extract significantly boost the proliferation of HepG2 cells. But the anti-cancer potential may differ from cell line to cell line hence further investigation is required for evaluating the cytotoxic action of leaves of *Punica granatum*.

The results of present *in vitro* investigation, evidently illustrate that all five tested extracts of leaves of *Punica granatum* significantly enhance the glucose uptake by yeast cells via insulinotropic action and primarily n-hexane extract inhibits α -amylase enzyme activity. Therefore, *Punica granatum* leaves are reported to have anti-diabetic potential by inhibiting α -amylase enzyme as well as by increasing the glucose uptake by yeast cells.

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